

**DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' THINKING AND USE OF MODERN
TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN ORGANIZING EDUCATIONAL LESSONS IN
OTML**

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Annotation:

the organization of training sessions, the use of information technologies, the development of student thinking, pedagogical technologies, modern teaching technologies, the content of training sessions are mentioned.

Keywords: educational process, lesson, pedagogical goal, development of thinking, lesson methodology, training topics, activity content.

Introduction

The development of students' thinking and the use of modern pedagogical technologies play an important role in the organization of educational activities in higher educational institutions. In the modern information society, the main attention is focused on the development of independent work and critical thinking skills and competencies of students from the transmission of knowledge.

Therefore, the use of modern pedagogical technologies is a necessary tool for effective education. One of these technologies is interactive learning, which allows students to become active participants in the learning process. They can independently search for information, solve problems, discuss and analyze material, which helps to develop their critical thinking.

The method of project activity is also actively used, which involves students performing certain tasks, for example, creating presentations, research projects or analyzing specific situations.

This method allows students to apply the acquired knowledge in practical situations, to form planning, organization and analysis skills.

In addition, distance and online forms of education have become increasingly popular in recent years, which also serve to develop the thinking of students. With dedicated platforms and apps, students can access educational information and complete assignments whenever and wherever is convenient for them. This allows them to work independently and develop time management skills.

Organization, management and development of the educational process in higher education institutions, including the organization, management and development of training sessions, increasing the quality of education in ensuring the performance of the specified goals and tasks, applying advanced pedagogical and information technologies to the process of training sessions in order to improve their content, conducting them in an interactive way, forming independent thinking skills in students, activities such as increasing activity, completing problematic tasks, etc. In this context, we emphasize the need to widely use the following concepts:

- equipping auditoriums with modern technical equipment and using them effectively in training sessions, organizing this process in small groups;

- determining the logical-structural form of educational activities in each educational direction, strengthening them to the requirements of immediate life, enriching them with problematic assignments, and preparing group recommendations and instructions;

- to establish the use of pedagogical and information technologies and interactive devices in training sessions;

- to deliver handouts on the subjects of the training sessions held according to the variation courses to the learners and to prepare for them cavolles on each topic, thus ensuring that they come to the training prepared;

- paying special attention to the content of the questions prepared and given by the students, depending on the quality of the questions, determining their state of preparation for specific subjects of the training session, achieving the formation of the skills of thinking, independent knowledge, finding, using and analyzing literature on the subject;

- mutual discussion of the information collected by the students on the topic of training sessions, analysis of critical and independent opinions, summarizing them;

- revitalization of scientific and technical research in groups;

- to strengthen the activity of internal control departments in order to realize that pedagogues approach their tasks responsibly and holistically in imparting knowledge to learners, and to conduct interviews among them on the topic "Educators in the eyes of learners" and discuss the results in detail;

- study of foreign experiences on improving the quality of training, generalization and development of school manuals on those that can be used in the republic.

Based on these tasks, we conclude that in order for students to independently think modernly, choose and implement professional activities, they should have the following qualities:

- ability to see problems;
- to understand their reasons for being creative;
- summarizing observed events with acquired knowledge;
- summarizing and generating new knowledge ;

- replacing several concepts with one common one;
- to distinguish between many cases;
- to express one's opinion correctly and in detail;
- quickly and accurately find the necessary information;
- problem analysis and evaluation;
- finish the job;

change the direction of thinking in response to a change in the situation;

- development of thinking.

Developing thinking includes:

Develop thinking

Analytical thinking	Formation of skills to distinguish important signs and forces.
Synthesizing thinking	Development of skills that establish a plan of educational materials, common symbols and overall efficiency.
Analytical synthesizer	To develop the skills of classifying facts, making generalizations.
Abstract thinking	Separating important and common signs, distinguishing unimportant signs, applying knowledge in practice.

Examples of teaching technologies that can be used in training include:

- creative;
- designing;
- problematic;
- informational and telecommunication;
- automated;
- programmed.

You can choose one of these. A teaching technician may have the following duties:

- ✓ linear;
- ✓ branched;
- ✓ adaptive;
- ✓ generalized;
- ✓ dactur-algorithmic;
- ✓ block teaching;
- ✓ modular training;
- ✓ full mastery of knowledge.

Modern teaching technologies

Creative	Technology that continuously forms the creative thinking of learners and develops their abilities. Its purpose is to awaken creativity in students and develop their creative potential.
Projecting	Pedagogical process diagram, trainings are conducted and a technological map is created. His goal is to activate his existing knowledge and acquire new ones so that students can actively engage in design activities in the socio-cultural environment.
Problematic	Developmental teaching is a technology that stimulates the process of

	active learning and forms a logical sequence of thinking. The essence of problem-based teaching is to manage the activity of acquiring new knowledge by the pedagogue by organizing problematic situations in education and solving educational (good, life) problems, problems and questions.
Information and telecommunication	It is a set of information transfer devices, processing and using knowledge using computers and telecommunication devices. The level of information technology in education is evaluated depending on the level of provision of both computers and technical devices.
Automatic	Makes it possible to independently learn the subject or a large part of it. This system combines simple exercises, a set of exercises, laboratory exercises, a reference and an expert checking the acquired information, provides an optimal way to study educational materials, strengthens the skills of analysis and research, and allows to save the time of learners.
Programmed	This is a technology that provides an opportunity to independently acquire knowledge, skills, and abilities with the help of specially developed computer training devices (computer, simulator, computer training).

It should be emphasized that in traditional education students are taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge, teaching with the help of modern technologies teaches them to independently search, analyze and draw conclusions about the knowledge they need to acquire. They have always been one of the most urgent problems in the education system regarding the development and improvement of knowledge . At the same time, it is necessary to develop pedagogical technologies in the educational process and implement them with the help of information technologies.

Thus, the development of students' thinking and the use of modern pedagogical technologies are components of the organization of educational activities in universities. They allow students to actively participate in the educational process, work independently, develop critical thinking skills, and apply the acquired knowledge in practice.

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